

Effect of *Nasya* and *Swedana* in the Management of Cervical Spondylosis – A Case Report

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ABSTRACT: Cervical Spondylosis (CS) is a chronic degenerative condition of cervical spine causing neck pain, suboccipital pain, vertigo, shoulder pain, numbness in upper limbs and reduced range of motion of neck. The prevalence of Cervical Spondylosis was 13% in the third decade and 5% in the fourth decade. It is the most common emerging problem in today's era with limited range of allopathic regime. The symptoms of Cervical Spondylosis coincide with *Manyastambha* in *Ayurveda*. The present case study aimed to focus on the evaluation of the effect of *Valuka Sweda*, *Nasya* with *Karpasthyadi Taila* for 4 days and *Ksheera Bala Taila* for next 3 days followed by *Nirgundi Patra Pinda Sweda* for next 7 days in Cervical Spondylosis and a significant relief was found in the symptoms.

KEYWORDS: Cervical Spondylosis(CS), *Nasya*, *Karpasthyadi Taila*(KT), *Nirgundi Patra Pinda Sweda* (NPPS).

INTRODUCTION

Cervical Spondylosis is degeneration of the bones, discs and joints of the neck caused by the normal wear and tear of aging[1]. With age, the discs of cervical spine gradually break down, lose fluid and become stiffer[2]. Spondylotic changes are common in 70% of women and 95% of men at age of 65 and 60 respectively[3]. Aging is a major factor responsible for the CS but previous injury to neck, certain occupations like gymnasts and poor posture might also play a role in the development of spinal changes that result in CS. CS can be correlated to *Manyastambha* as described in *Ayurveda*.

According to *Acharya Sushruta*, due to improper sleeping posture, day sleep, improper bed *Kaphavritta Vata Dosha* results in *Manyastambha*[5]. In *Chikitsa Sthana Acharya Sushruta* indicated *Vatakaphanashaka Nasya* and *Ruksha Sweda* in *Manyastambha*[6]. *Valuka Sweda* is a type of *Ruksha Sweda* which pacifies the *avarana* of *Kapha*.

As degeneration is an implication of *Aptarpana*. Hence the degenerative changes in the vertebrae and intervertebral disk associated in CS need nourishment or *Brimhana* therapy. As the pain can't occur without *Vataprakopa*[7] and as there is *Kapha Avarana* hence *Karpasthyadi Taila* was selected because of its *Vatakaphashamaka* properties and *Ksheerabala Taila* for its *balya* properties. The drug is administered through nasal route (*Nasya*) as vitiated *dosha* should be removed through its closest pathway. As there is associated stiffness and pain at cervical region in cervical spondylosis *Nirgundi Patra Pinda Sweda* relieves paravertebral muscle spasm and pain. *Nirgundi* has anti inflammatory and analgesic effect[10]. So this trial was undertaken to evaluate the efficacy of *nasya* with *Karpasthayadi Taila* followed by *Nirgundi Patra Pinda Sweda* in reducing the sign and symptoms of Cervical Spondylosis.

MATERIAL & METHODS

Case report- A female patient of age 50 years visited to the OPD of Panchakarma Department with complaints of pain, stiffness & restricted movements at cervical region, pain radiating to bilaterally shoulder region, numbness and tingling sensation, headache, vertigo, since past 2-3 years. Patient was on propranolol 40 mg since 2years.

Investigations

Hematological investigations including Hb, ESR, urine test, Random blood sugar, uric acid & blood urea were done before the treatment to rule out other systematic diseases. All were within normal limits.

MRI Scan dated April 2017 depicted:

Cervical disc desiccation, osteophyte complex at C4-C5 intervertebral disc level causing indentation over thecal sac.

Criteria for assessment–

The improvement in the patient was assessed on the basis of relief in the signs and symptoms of the disease. All the signs and symptoms were given scoring depending upon their severity to assess the effect of the treatment objectively[4].(Kumar Jayadip P Shah et al)

Table no. 1- PAIN SCORE

No Pain	0
Pain in the neck, mildly aggravates with movement	1
Pain in neck, severly aggravates with movement	2
Mild or severe pain with radiation to arm	3
Pain in neck with radiation and disturbed the sleep	4

Table no.2 –STIFFNESS SCORE

No Stiffness	0
Stiffness (needs no medication)	1
Stiffness (relives by external analgesic application)	2
Stiffness (relives by medication)	3
Stiffness (no relief with medication)	4

Table no.3-TENDERNESS SCORE

No tenderness	0
Mild pain on deep pressure	1
Moderate pain on deep pressure	2
Severe pain on deep pressure	3
Unbearable pain on touch at the site	4

Table no.4 –HEADACHE SCORE

No headache	0
mild pain occasionally	1
headache once in a week	2
headache > 5 times a week	3
daily severe headache	4

Table no.5 –VERTIGO SCORE

No vertigo	0
vertigo Upto 1hr	1
vertigo Upto 2hrs	2
vertigo Upto 3hrs	3
vertigo More than 3hrs	4

Table no. 6 -TINGLING SENSATION SCORE

Absent	0
Occasional	1
Up to 1hr	2
Up to 2hrs	3
More than 3hrs	4

Range of movement-

Table no. 7 – FLEXION SCORE

No restriction i.e. able to touch the interclavicular line	0
Up to 2cms difference between the chin and interclavicular line	1
2-4cms difference between the chin and interclavicular line	2
More than 4cms difference	3

Table no. 8 - EXTENSION SCORE

Normal i.e. able to extend the head up to the level where the tip of nose and forehead lie in horizontal plane (approximately flexion to extension -130°)	0
Movement up to 120°	1
Movement up to 110°- 120°	2
Movement less than 110°	3

Table no. 9 - LATERAL ROTATION SCORE

Normal i.e. able to perform complete rotation of neck	0
Complete rotation with little difficulty	1
Side to side rotation only	2
One side rotation only	3
Complete restriction of movement	4

Table no. 10 - LATERAL FLEXION SCORE

Normal i.e. the ear touches to the shoulder tip	0
Up to 3cms difference between the ear and shoulder tip	1
3 – 5cms difference between the ear and shoulder tip	2
More than 5cms difference between the ear and shoulder tip	3

Treatment plan-

- *Valuka Sweda* in the morning from 1st – 7th day.
- *Nasya* with *Karpasthyadi Taila* from 1st – 4th day.

Ingradients of *Karpasthyadi Taila*[8]-

Kwatha Dravya – *Karpasa Asthi, Bala, Masha, Kulattha.*

Kalka Dravya – *Devadaru, Balamula, Rasna, Kushta, Sarshapa, Nagara, Shigru, Punarnava.*

Taila – *Tila Taila.*

Milk – goat milk

- *Nasya* with *Ksheerabala Taila* on 5th – 7th day.

Ingradients of *Ksheerabala Taila*[9] -

Kalka Dravya – *Balamoola*

Milk – cow's milk

Taila – *Tila Taila*

- *Nirgundi Patra Pinda Swedana* from 7th- 14th day.

Shamana drugs-

Pathyadi Kwatha 20 gm BD empty stomach for 14 days.

Kaishora Guggulu 2 tablets thrice a day with leukwarm water for 14 days.

Amapachana Vati. 2 tablets thrice a day with leukwarm water before meal for 14 days .

Method of Nasya

Purvakarma – *Abhyanga* with *Bala Taila* followed by *Vashpa Sweda* over the facial are was done.

Pradhanakarma – *Nasya* with *Karpasthyadi Taila* was done for 4 days followed by *Nasya* with *Ksheerabala Taila* for 3 days in following doses as there was burning sensation over neck, both shoulders on 4th day of *Nasya* with KT, so it had been changed to *Ksheerabala taila* for last 3 days.

Table no. 11-Drug and dose of Nasya

Day	Oil used	Dose
Day -1	<i>Karpasthayadi taila</i>	2 <i>bindu</i> (1ml)in each nostril
Day-2	<i>Karpasthayadi taila</i>	4 <i>bindu</i> in each nostril
Day-3	<i>Karpasthayadi taila</i>	6 <i>bindu</i> in each nostril
Day-4	<i>Karpasthayadi taila</i>	8 <i>bindu</i> in each nostril
Day-5	<i>Ksheerabala taila</i>	8 <i>bindu</i> in each nostril
Day-6	<i>Ksheerabala taila</i>	4 <i>bindu</i> in each nostril
Day-7	<i>Ksheerabala taila</i>	4 <i>bindu</i> in each nostril

Paschat Karma– After completion of *Nasya* procedure *Ushdoka Kavala* was done.

Nirgundi Patra Pinda Swedana–

A *Pottali* was made of hot bolus of *Nirgundi* leaves (fried in oil) which was applied over the neck and shoulder region in circular motion for 15-20 minutes.

Result–A highly significant result was observed in symptoms of Cervical Spondylosis measured on the basis of scoring pattern before and after the treatment.

Table no. 12- Effect on Symptoms

S. no.	Symptoms	BT	AT
1	Pain	3	1
2	Stiffness	3	1
3	Tenderness	3	1
4	Headache	4	2

5	Vertigo	1	0
6	Tingling sensation	0	0

Effect on range of movement –

Table no.13-

S. no.	Range of movement	BT	AT
1	Flexion	2	0
2	Extension	0	0
3	Lateral flexion	1	0
4	Lateral rotation	0	0

DISCUSSION

Effect of Nasya -Cervical Spondylosis is one of the common emerging problem now a days due to changing life style. There are several factors involved in pathogenesis like old age, trauma, improper sitting and sleeping posture, excessive travelling etc. As *Manyasandhi* is the seat of *Shleshaka Kapha* and the early degenerative changes shows *Kapha-Vata* predominance. Hence *Nasya* was specifically selected as *Manyasandhi* is one among *Urdhwajatrugata* body part. *Nasya* is the best line of treatment in the management of *Urdhwajatrugata Vikara*.

For this *Karpasasthyadi Taila* was specifically selected for *Nasya* followed by *Ksheerabala Taila Nasya* to correct the underline pathology. *Karpasasthyadi Taila* has *Shothhara* (anti-inflammatory), *Shulaprashamana* (analgesic) and *Vatashamaka* in nature. It helps in clearing the obstruction of *Kapha* by reducing stiffness. The *Ksheerabala Taila* is *balya* and *Rasyana* in nature hence gave nourishment to *Asthi Dhatu* and reduced further degeneration.

Effect of Nirgundi Patra Pinda Sweda- *Patrapinda Sweda* was done as local treatment. As *Swedana* has *Stambaghna*, *Gauravaghna*, *Sheetaghna* properties, it relaxed muscles and improved local blood circulation reduced stiffness, improved the range of movement. *Nirgundi* too is anti-inflammatory and analgesic in nature so it added to the effects of *swedana*. As a whole *NPPS* relieved paravertebral muscle spasm & pain, strengthened paravertebral muscles & resulted in local anti-inflammatory effect.

Effect of Shamana therapy:

The contents of *Pathyadi Kwatha* had *tikta rasa* and *aampachaka* properties.

Kaishor Guggulu is *Vatashamaka*, *shothanashaka* and *lekhana* in nature with *pitta* pacifying properties. It helped in reducing the burning sensation of neck. *Aampachaka Vati* removed *Kapha Avarana* and facilitated proper movement of *Vata*.

CONCLUSION

From above case study it is observed that the symptoms of Cervical Spondylosis can be managed easily by *Panchakarma* therapy along with oral *ayurvedic* regime.

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